

of several bands in the region 1 650–1 540 cm^{-1} associated with the vibrational modes of aromatic amine ring^{5,12-14}.

Molar conductivities of none of these complexes approached either ideal or a 1 : 1 electrolyte¹⁵. Molar conductivities of the present complexes were indicative of their dissociation in *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone solution.

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Potentiometric Studies on the Complex Equilibria in the Quaternary Systems. Copper(II)/Nickel(II)/Zinc(II)—Picolinic Acid—Oxalic Acid—Catechol

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EXTENSIVE studies have been carried out on ternary¹⁻⁴ systems involving transition metal ions, employing a variety of physicochemical techniques, but much less work has been reported on quaternary system⁵⁻¹⁰. In view of this, it has been considered of interest to investigate quaternary mixed ligand complexes of some of the common metal ions of first transition series of the type,

$M(\text{II})\text{-Pic-Ox-Cat}$, where $M(\text{II}) = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$; Pic = picolinic acid, Ox = oxalic acid, Cat = catechol. Formation constants and free energy of formation have also been evaluated at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ ($\mu = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 \text{ M KNO}_3$) from which the formation constant at zero ionic concentration has been graphically obtained.

Experimental

Stock solutions of metal nitrates were prepared in double-distilled water and standardised by the usual methods¹¹. The ligand solutions of Ox, Pic and Cat were prepared by direct weighing. The total volume of the solution (50 ml) and the concentration ($5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) in metal and ligands were kept constant at the beginning of each titration.

Calculation: The dissociation constants of the ligand were determined by the method of Chaberek and Martell¹². The formation constants ($\log K_{\text{MAB}}$) of the ternary complex MAB formed by the simultaneous addition of A and B to the metal ion, were calculated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa¹³ as extended by Kumar *et al.*¹⁴. $\log K_{\text{MABC}}$ for the quaternary species formed by the stepwise addition of catechol to the initially formed ternary species MAB were evaluated by the method of Thompson and Loraas¹⁵. The overall stability constants of the quaternary complex obtained by summing up the respective values of $\log K_{\text{MAB}}$ and $\log K_{\text{MABC}}$ have been recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Curves for the system $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Pic-Ox-Cat}$ (Fig. 1) have been discussed as representative. The curves and the discussion of the other systems involving $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ being identical have been avoided for the sake of brevity. Curves (c) and (d) depicting inflections at $m=1$ and $m=2$ ($m = \text{moles of the base added per mole of metal ion or ligand}$) represent the titration of Pic and Ox, respectively. No well-defined inflection in the case of cat (curve b) is, however, observed indicating the non-labile nature of phenolic proton. Curves (e), (f) and (g) exhibit the titration of 1 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Ox/Cat/Pic}$ systems, respectively^{16,17}.

In the systems 1 : 1 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Pic-Cat}$ (curve h) and $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Ox-Cat}$ (curve i), Pic/Ox acts as primary ligand and the catechol as the secondary one. Thus the ternary complex formation occurs by the stepwise addition of the ligands to the metal ion as is evidenced by the inflections observed at $m=1$ and 3 or $m=2$ and 4 in the respective curves. However, in the system 1 : 1 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Ox-Pic}$ (curve j), lowering in pH followed by a single sharp inflection at $m=3$ may be attributed to the simultaneous addition of both the ligands to the metal ion forming metal-biligand species. The formation of ternary species is further supported by the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curves^{18,19}

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TABLE 1

System	$\log K_{MLL'}^M$			$\log K_{MLL'L}^{MLL'}$			Overall formation constant			$\log K_o$	ΔG° kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹		
	$\mu=$	0.1	0.2	0.3	μ	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1			0.2	0.3
Cu ^{II} -Ox-Pic-Cat		8.85 ± 0.12	8.88 ± 0.09	8.78 ± 0.19		9.98 ± 0.20	9.90 ± 0.20	9.84 ± 0.15	18.83	18.73	18.62	19.10	-26.03
Ni ^{II} -Ox-Pic-Cat		8.41 ± 0.17	8.92 ± 0.20	8.20 ± 0.20		6.57 ± 0.16	6.50 ± 0.11	6.42 ± 0.09	14.98	14.82	14.62	15.20	-20.71
Zn ^{II} -Ox-Pic-Cat		7.87 ± 0.20	7.89 ± 0.17	7.79 ± 0.14		7.58 ± 0.16	7.52 ± 0.18	7.46 ± 0.18	18.45	15.95	15.25	15.50	-21.12

Fig. 1. System 1:1:1:1 Cu^{II}-Ox-Pic-Cat: (b) Cat, (c) Pic, (d) Ox, (e) Cu^{II}-Ox, (f) Cu^{II}-Cat, (g) Cu^{II}-Pic, (h) Cu^{II}-Pic-Cat, (i) Cu^{II}-Ox-Cat, (j) Cu^{II}-Ox-Pic, (k) Cu^{II}-Ox-Pic-Cat, and (T, T', X, X') theoretical composite curves; (→) appearance of ppt.

(x and x' in case of Cu^{II}-Ox-Pic and T in case of Cu^{II}-Pic-Cat and Cu^{II}-Ox-Cat, respectively).

Curve (k), representing the system 1:1:1:1 Cu^{II}-Pic-Ox-Cat, superimposes the curve (j) upto $m=3$ indicating the initial formation of 1:1:1 Cu^{II}-Pic-Ox complex. The addition of tertiary ligand catechol, however, takes place at a later stage. Lowering of pH, colour change from light blue to bottle green and a buffer region followed by a well-defined inflection at $m=5$, give evidences for the quaternary species, the formation of which is further supported by non-formation of precipitate during the titration and the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curves T' (drawn

by adding the horizontal distances of the curves for 1:1:1 Cu^{II}-Pic-Ox systems and the tertiary ligand with the experimental curve k for the quaternary system) in the region of its formation.

A comparison of the data of the formation constants for the ternary as well as quaternary complexes given in the Table 1, indicates the following order of stabilities in terms of metal ions (Williams-Irving order²⁰), Zn^{II} < Cu^{II} > Ni^{II}.

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